

WP3A4. Open Access Educational Materials for Academic Staff

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Baltics4UA: Supporting Ukraine through citizen engagement at Baltic Universities

Deliverable Factsheet

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Consortium

The consortium governing the project is adequately representing a wide range of expertise, as 5 Higher Education Institutions (Tallinn University, Lviv Polytechnic National University, Kaunas University of Technology, University of Tartu, University of Latvia) join hands with a web education specialist (Web2Learn). This mix of knowledge, skills, experiences and networks guarantees a layered approach toward a diverse range of stakeholders.

	Name	Short Name	Country
1	Tallinn University	TLU	Estonia
2	Lviv Polytechnic National University	LPNU	Ukraine
3	Web2Learn	W2L	Greece
4	Kaunas University of Technology	KTU	Lithuania
5	University of Tartu	UT	Estonia
6	University of Latvia	LV	Latvia

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Baltics4UA: Supporting Ukraine through citizen engagement at Baltic Universities

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List of Abbreviations

The following table presents the acronyms used in the deliverable in alphabetical order.

Abbreviations

Description

HEI

Higher Education Institution

Baltics4UA: Supporting Ukraine through citizen engagement at Baltic Universities

Executive Summary

This document provides open-access educational materials aimed at enhancing citizen engagement, drawing on the experiences of the Baltics4UA partners. Through practical case studies, this document showcases different methods of integrating citizen engagement into the classroom, such as workshop for academic staff, experience café, world café, hackathon, art event, youth debate tournament. These case studies present successful formats and offer insightful reflections on organizing citizen engagement activities. These formats are designed to increase citizen engagement, particularly in responding to humanitarian crises, such as the full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022.

1. Introduction to Baltics4UA

Since the full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022, the Baltic states have become a refuge for Ukrainians fleeing the war. This humanitarian crisis underlines the urgent need to upskill higher education (HE) staff and bolster the capacity of Baltic HE institutions in crisis response, developing mechanisms that effectively mobilize and engage citizens for social purposes and fostering resilience.

In response to this need, the Baltics4UA consortium has been formed, bringing together forward-looking and innovation-oriented universities in the Baltic states and Ukraine (Tallinn University, University of Tartu, University of Latvia, Kaunas University of Technology, Lviv Polytechnic National University) along with the experienced industry and business partner Web2Learn. The consortium aims to address these issues by organizing diverse citizen engagement activities and uniting academic staff, students, citizens, local communities, and regional and national stakeholders across the Baltic countries.

The main objectives of the Baltics4UA project, thus, focus on three key areas:

1. Strengthen the social responsibility of Baltic universities by implementing civic engagement initiatives to support the Ukrainian humanitarian crisis in the Baltic region.
2. Mobilize Baltic universities to benefit Ukrainian communities by engaging quadruple helix actors—science, policy, industry, and society.
3. Foster innovative educational practices and upskill staff at Baltic HEIs through cross-cultural dialogue, citizen involvement, and business-academia collaboration.

2. Rationale of open access education materials

These open-access educational materials aim to provide academic staff insights on engaging diverse groups in citizen engagement actions. By showcasing selected cases, the material demonstrates how citizen engagement actions have been integrated into various HEIs of the Baltics4UA consortium. This guide includes a detailed description of the format of citizen engagement actions, along with practical tips and recommendations for classroom integration. Additionally, it provides links to supplementary materials developed as part of the Baltics4UA project, offering detailed insights and descriptions of specific project actions undertaken by the partners.

This material targets higher education professionals, specifically teaching and administrative staff interested in incorporating citizen engagement into their teaching practices and curriculum as part of broader institutional strategies. This guide will support their efforts to integrate citizen engagement actions sustainably.

3. Why teach citizen engagement?

Before describing the importance of teaching civic education, one needs to define how the following concept would be defined and applied in the following material. According to Rietbergen-McCracken (2012), civic education can be defined as “the provision of information and learning experiences to equip and empower citizens to participate in democratic processes (p. 1).” Civic education can be delivered through different means, such as in-person classroom-based experience and extra-curricular and informal activities, including training and experiential learning (ibid.).

Over the last decades, there has been a growing emphasis on fostering young people's understanding of civic matters and cultivating their inclination to participate actively in democratic processes and society (“Understanding Youth Engagement,” 2023). Thus, integrating civic education into the curriculum is a vital mechanism that can help develop young people's skills and competencies as active citizens and members of society.

Previous scholarly literature indicates that civic education is often seen as a solution for many challenges faced by contemporary society as civic education provides the medium and framework to address issues arising from globalization, multiculturalism, migration, the impact of information and communication technologies, and declining civic engagement, and the imperative to foster social conscience and encourage active social participation (Arbués, 2014). Moreover, it is perceived as a means to combat the individualism that often separates individuals from their communities (Arbués, 2014).

In the European context, the Council of Europe has issued several recommendations and guidance for the governments that aim to educate young people in democratic citizenship and bolster educational reforms on efficient ways of integrating this component into the curriculum (Council of Europe, 2010b).

Despite these efforts, the recent study conducted by IEA, together with ACER (Australian Council for Educational Research) and LUMSA (Libera Università Maria SS. Assunta) University, unveils that there was no increase in civic knowledge among the countries that participated in both 2016 and 2022 (Schulz et al., 2022).

In this respect, it is important to find new and innovative ways to encourage young people to actively participate in democratic processes and be societally engaged by equipping them with the necessary tools and information to navigate this process. The

universities and other educational institutions play an important role in the following process by providing the necessary infrastructure and expertise and creating a learning environment to facilitate the development of competencies necessary for active citizenship.

Universities also serve as an important hub for mobilizing students and other relevant stakeholders to engage directly in various initiatives to address social issues. The example of the Baltic HEIs in addressing the humanitarian crisis and supporting Ukrainian communities as a result of the full-scale invasion of Ukraine by Russia is one of the examples of social and civic activism. The next section of the guide will provide educators with practical tips on integrating the following initiative into the classroom setting.

4. How to integrate citizen engagement initiatives in the classroom? Practical case studies

This section provides an overview of the various formats of citizen engagement activities implemented by the Baltics4UA consortium partners. Specifically, there are 6 case studies: 1) workshop for academic staff on organizing citizen engagement actions, 2) experience café, 3) world café in a workshop “universities empowering students and citizens for social action: citizen engagement as crisis response,” 4) hackathons in action: Baltic universities join forces to help Ukraine, 5) art events, 6) youth debate tournament. Each is described in detail to facilitate easy implementation and integration of citizen engagement actions in the classroom by anyone interested in running such initiatives. Every case study embodies the best practices and expertise represented by the consortium partners. Furthermore, this document includes links to relevant publications produced based on the formats and, in some cases, required to execute these initiatives.

1. Workshop for academic staff on organizing citizen engagement actions

This workshop is tailored specifically for university staff members to enhance their skills in organizing citizen engagement initiatives. The foundation of the training is the policy brief titled “Higher education in humanitarian crises: resilience, social inclusion, innovation.” This document offers practical recommendations and best practices for organizing and leading citizen engagement initiatives.

The workshop’s structure is designed into three key parts: Introduction, Practice, and Conclusion. It begins with a policy brief presentation, highlighting the main lessons and

formats for citizen engagement actions. Participants are then divided into groups, with tables evenly arranged to facilitate collaboration. Each group uses a printed template to design their own citizen engagement activities, applying the policy recommendations practically. Following this, teams present their ideas, receive feedback, and suggest improvements to one another.

Table 1. Recommendations to prepare the workshop for academic staff on organizing citizen engagement actions.

Structure	First, divide the event into three parts: Introduction, Practice, and Conclusion. During the introduction, organizers should present a policy brief to participants, explaining the main lessons learned and potential formats for organizing citizen engagement actions. These can later be implemented during the second part of the event.
Group Formation/Space Arrangement	If you conduct this activity in a classroom, it is better for group work if tables are arranged evenly throughout the room, ensuring each team sits at its own table.
Template for event organization	We recommend printing out the template for organizing citizen engagement actions for the second part of the training. This template ensures that participants can practically apply knowledge from the policy brief. Each question in the policy brief is explained in the template, making it easy to follow and fill out without prior knowledge.
Presentation of the planned event	Giving participants time to reflect on what has been discussed is vital. Hence, teams should present their ideas to each other. After the presentation, participants from other groups asked questions and suggested ideas on how the team could improve their event.

Supplementing Materials:

The links below contain supplementary materials required for implementing the format.

1. [Methodology](#)

In a step-by-step approach, the methodology outlines how to set up a citizen engagement action within and beyond academia (Oikonomou, Boichenko, & Zourou, 2023)

2. [Study](#)

The study analyzes 20 academia-driven citizen engagement actions in the Baltics to support Ukrainian refugees and displaced persons (Zourou, Oikonomou, & Samiotis, 2023).

3. [Policy Brief](#)

The document details the lessons learned from conducting 23 citizen engagement initiatives. Additionally, it includes various types of citizen engagement actions that can serve as inspiration for designing an event using a template (Kondratyck, Gibson, & Beitane, 2024a)

4. [Template for organizing citizen engagement actions](#)

The printout material needed for the group work contains essential points based on the policy brief, which must be considered before implementing a citizen engagement action (Kondratyck, Gibson, & Beitane, 2024b).

2. Experience Café

The event's purpose is to discuss and share experiences on cooperation in social actions initiated by academia, particularly in the context of responding to crisis situations. Participants will be able to learn about examples of successful initiatives and discuss opportunities for expansion and improvement. Significant attention should also be paid to scenarios that did not have the intended outcome, so discussing the reasons and consequences of such actions is also advisable. As a result, the event participants can generate proposals that will form the basis for further improvement of crisis management mechanisms in universities and help increase the preparation level for risks and challenges.

The event featured interactive activities, where all participants worked in small teams under the guidance of their leaders. When organizing an Experience Café, it is important to provide interactive activities that facilitate effective interaction between participants, exchange of experiences, and generation of new ideas. Such activities can include:

1. Workshops and working groups: Participants should be divided into small groups to discuss specific topics or issues. Each group can work on different aspects of cooperation in social action or crises.
2. Role-playing and scenario-based methods: Participants take on the roles of different stakeholders and work on solving a specific crisis.
3. Brainstorming sessions to generate new ideas for cooperation and problem-solving.
4. Idea Gallery method: Participants can create posters or infographics with their ideas and solutions and then display them in a gallery.

Table 2. Recommendations to prepare the experience café

The purpose of the event	The purpose of the event should be clearly defined, for example, to improve cooperation between the management of the HEI and the academic community for effective response to crises.
Format	Discussion of issues at tables allows participants to periodically change places to discuss new topics. Several tables with different discussion topics should be prepared in advance, in accordance with the purpose of the event.
Audience	It is important to invite key representatives from university administration, researchers, teachers, and students who have experience or interest in crisis management.
Program	It is necessary to develop a detailed program in advance, featuring a clear schedule of speeches, group discussions, and training sessions.
Event stages	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The facilitator introduces the rules of the activity. Participants are divided into groups of 3-7 people. Each group should choose a leader. 2. The group generates ideas according to the task set by the facilitator. The group leader records them. It is important that no thesis is criticized. The discussion takes 10-20 minutes. 3. The group leaders move to another table, and the facilitator introduces the participants to the results. Participants refine concepts, delete unsuccessful ones, and suggest new ones. After 5-15 minutes, the next table is changed, and so on - until the leaders return to their groups. 4. Group leaders share the results of their work with their original teams and come up with the 5 best ideas in their opinion. 5. Each group presents the best ideas to all participants.
Event results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A deep understanding of the complex issues of cooperation in social actions, consolidation of various ideas and proposals, and development of joint solutions for effective response to crises. ● Strengthening of interaction and cooperation, formulation of recommendations and strategies for further actions.

Supplementing Materials:

1. Event program (printed programs with session schedules and information about key speakers),
2. Working materials (printed materials for each session, including action plan, feedback forms, analytical reports, etc.)
3. Resources for group work (flipcharts, markers, stickers)
4. Information brochures on best practices in crisis management, guidelines and manuals.

3. World Café in a workshop “Universities empowering students and citizens for social action: citizen engagement as crisis response”

World Café is an excellent method for integrating citizen engagement initiatives in the classroom when there are more than 20 participants who possess adequate previous knowledge or experience on the topic. It allows them to share their understanding, collaborate, and create concepts. This method can be used during regular classes, or special events can be organized.

When preparing the World Café plan, it's crucial to pinpoint the exact topic along with the key challenges where you aim to gather people's opinions and solutions. You might consider having a brainstorming session with your team to identify the most relevant questions. At Tallinn University (TLU), we accounted for the activities offered to Ukrainian refugees in Estonia by various organizations and institutions and discovered there was a significant lack of support for refugees to continue their educational pathways. Delving deeper into the topic, our World Café focused on the question of how to support Ukrainian refugees in achieving their educational aspirations in Estonia.

Once the topic is set, finding the relevant participants is crucial. This involves mapping different stakeholders who have any responsibilities or contact with refugees. In line with inclusive practice, it's also important to consider how to engage the refugees themselves and invite them to participate. At Tallinn University (TLU), we invited participants for the World Café from a range of groups, including public bodies (such as the Ministry of Education and Research, Social Insurance Board, and Integration Foundation), public schools and universities, community services (for example, libraries, youth centers, and summer camps), as well as students and academic staff from lifelong learning disciplines.

For organizing the World Café, there are several basic practical components to consider, as outlined by The World Café Community Foundation (2024). Arrange the room so there are, preferably, round tables with 5–6 chairs around each. Equip each table with an A1 white flipchart, a few markers in different colors (preferably water-based markers to prevent damage to the tables as they don't leak through the paper), sticky notes, and some pens. Coordinate with your colleagues or more experienced students to act as table hosts. Their role is to guide participants in the

roundtable discussion and to record the ideas and results on the flipchart. Table hosts begin each discussion from the second round by providing a brief overview (2 minutes) of the ideas that were highlighted previously. They are also responsible for keeping time and ensuring that each participant at the table gets a chance to speak.

World Café functions such that each round table covers a domain related to the topic, with specific questions posed for different rounds to be answered at each table. Twenty minutes is considered the optimal time for each round. After this period, participants leave their current table, with each member moving to a different, new table. Table hosts facilitate the discussions at their designated table throughout the entire event. In conclusion, they offer an overview of the ideas and results gathered, and the content recorded on the flip chart is shared with others.

The **domains** at the round tables could be associated with different stakeholders' roles, the target group, or another logical distinction pertinent to the topic. Based on the feedback collected from participants through the registration form, we identified five domains for discussion at the round tables:

- Elementary and high school studies
- Vocational and professional studies
- Higher, lifelong, and adult education
- Youth work and non-formal education at youth facilities
- Language studies

The questions in each round should lead closer to a solution by each step. The easiest way to form the questions for each round is to take some commonly known model or concept, e.g., SWOT analysis or the PDCA cycle. In that case, you may start by asking, in the first round, what are the strengths in this field. After 20 minutes, participants change; the table hosts briefly introduce the insights of the previous round, and new participants start to discuss what the inner weaknesses related to this domain are. The third round is about opportunities from outside the field, and the fourth round spotlights the threats to the domain. Therefore, the session would last approximately 1.5 hours (4 x 20 minutes for round tables, and 10 minutes for organization), in addition to starting and finalizing activities (5 minutes per table to introduce the results) should be taken into account, totaling 2 hours. For our World Café, we prepared questions for four rounds (see Table 3).

Stay positive, keep calm, be inclusive, and show genuine interest in the topic, participants' experiences, and feel as if you're in a regular café chatting with friends and acquaintances. You will see the World Café runs smoothly on its own.

Recommendations to prepare the format:

At the beginning of the session, establish a mentally safe room by agreeing on certain principles which, in some cases, are also referred to as Café Etiquette (The World Café Community Foundation, 2024). We preferred agreements to foster inclusivity. Ask each participant to write on paper what they need to feel free to speak and offer their own opinions. As a second step, participants at each table introduce their needs, which are then collected. As a final step, the session's facilitator asks each table to introduce their agreements and writes the agreements, which are agreed upon by participants, on the wall paper. The facilitator's responsibility is to ensure that agreements include confidentiality (identifiable information cannot be shared outside the session), non-judgmental communication, and that each participant's thoughts are heard. The agreements must be accepted, agreed upon, and followed by participants throughout the session. The facilitator and table-hosts observe and intervene if necessary.

There is a risk associated with participants, as individuals have vastly different experiences, both positive and negative, when working with refugees. Moreover, participating refugees might have experienced a range of services in addition to war trauma. It is crucial to ensure the best possible safety for each participant and, if necessary, to provide initial mental health support. During the preparation phase, you may decide whether to designate a "guard" who will respond as quickly as possible, or you may prepare the entire team to offer mental first aid.

Often participants, when entering the room, tend to sit together with people they are already familiar with. Use this as a good starting point to ease them into the topic. An icebreaker can be very effective, and you will find it easier to mix them up later for more varied discussions at different round tables. For example, you may start the session by asking people at each table to get to know each other and to find at least three similarities and three differences they have regarding the topic or on some other issues (such as hobbies, educational experiences, etc.).

It is important to clarify what happens with the **results**. It might serve an educational aim for participants or they might be a good input for organizations for further development. But also it could be a good resume for offering the media to change the attitudes or creating the values.

Table 3. The World Café event at Tallinn University on March 23, 2023, focused on the educational pathways of Ukrainian refugees.

Topic. Ukrainian refugees' educational pathway.	Table 1. General education	Table 2. Lifelong learning	Table 3. Youth work	Table 4. Language studies
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I round	What describes the educational field in concern of Ukrainian refugees? What are the success stories in this educational field about Ukrainian refugees?
II round	What are the challenges and problems in this educational field related to Ukrainian refugees?
III round	Who are the stakeholders in this educational field, and what is their role related to Ukrainian refugees? Including - how the Ukraine professionals, scientists are engaged in this field? How are the professionals in this field supported?
IV round	What can different organizations and stakeholders do in this educational field to keep the Ukraine refugees in their educational track? How to support Ukraine people in their educational institutions. What is the role and possibilities of higher education institutions to support the Ukraine refugees' participation in this educational field? What actions must be taken?

4. Hackathons in action: Baltic universities join forces to help Ukraine

Hackathons have emerged as a dynamic and innovative format for problem-solving and skill development, bringing together diverse groups to tackle pressing challenges through intensive collaboration. These events foster creativity, teamwork, and the practical application of knowledge, making them an effective tool for addressing complex issues in various fields. Hackathons typically span one or two days and are structured to maximize collaborative efforts and creative problem-solving. Participants, often from diverse backgrounds, are grouped into teams to work intensively on specific challenges. These challenges are designed to be relevant and impactful, encouraging participants to leverage their skills and knowledge in innovative ways. The hackathon format consists of several key components:

1. *Introduction and briefing.* The event begins with an introduction to the hackathon's objectives, rules, and timeline. Participants are briefed on the specific challenges they will tackle and the resources available to them.
2. *Team formation.* Participants are organized into teams, usually comprising individuals with varied skills and expertise. This diversity enhances the team's ability to approach problems from different angles and develop comprehensive solutions.

3. *Working sessions.* Teams engage in intensive working sessions, brainstorming, and developing their solutions. These sessions are often punctuated by short breaks to maintain energy levels and promote informal networking.
4. *Mentorship and guidance.* Expert mentors are available throughout the hackathon to provide guidance, answer questions, and offer feedback. This mentorship is crucial for helping teams refine their ideas and overcome obstacles.
5. *Presentations and judging.* At the end of the working sessions, teams present their solutions to a panel of judges. These presentations typically include demonstrations, explanations of the solution's impact, and the feasibility of implementation.
6. *Awards and recognition.* Judges evaluate the presentations based on criteria such as creativity, technical merit, and potential impact. Winning teams are often awarded prizes or recognition to celebrate their achievements.

Hackathons are designed for a wide range of participants, including students, university staff, and stakeholders from various sectors. *The primary target audience* often includes:

- students from different academic disciplines, promoting interdisciplinary collaboration;
- university staff, including faculty and researchers, who can provide academic insights and support;
- industry professionals and stakeholders who bring practical perspectives and resources.

Table 4. Recommendations to prepare the hackathons

Aspect	Recommendations
Objectives	Clearly define the hackathon's goals and expected outcomes. Example of our hackathon: "The goal of this hackathon is to develop innovative solutions using space data to monitor and protect cultural heritage sites in Ukraine. Expected outcomes include the creation of prototypes for monitoring tools, increased awareness of cultural heritage issues, and enhanced skills in data analysis among participants".
Structure	Divide the event into phases: introduction and briefing, team formation, working sessions, mentorship and guidance, presentations and judging, awards and recognition.
Materials	Provide templates: such as, project planning templates, data analysis worksheets, presentation outlines, and policy briefs related to the hackathon theme.

Mentorship	Include expert mentors to guide participants throughout the event. Mentors should have expertise in relevant areas such as space data analysis, cultural heritage, and project management.
Collaboration space	Arrange the space to facilitate teamwork and collaboration. Use virtual collaboration tools like Zoom, Microsoft Teams, or Google Meet for video conferencing. Utilize breakout rooms for team discussions and tools like Miro or Jamboard for brainstorming sessions. Special platforms like Devpost or HackerEarth can be used for managing submissions and judging.
Technology	Ensure reliable internet access and availability of necessary software and tools.
Feedback sessions	Schedule regular check-ins and feedback sessions with mentors and organizers. For a 1-2 day event, schedule check-ins every 2-3 hours. These can be brief meetings to discuss progress, address challenges, and provide feedback.
Risk management	Prepare for potential risks such as technical issues or participant dropouts with backup plans: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - have technical support on standby and backup equipment available; - have a plan for reassigning team members or merging teams if necessary.
Engagement	Foster an inclusive and motivating environment to encourage active participation and creativity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ensure all participants feel welcomed and valued, provide diverse and balanced teams; - use icebreakers, energizers, and motivational talks to keep energy levels high; - acknowledge and celebrate all efforts, not just the winning solutions.
Documentation	Keep detailed records of all activities, ideas, and solutions developed during the hackathon. Assign a scribe for each team to document progress, use shared digital platforms for collaboration, and ensure final presentations and prototypes are archived.

Supplementing Materials:

This document provides a comprehensive methodology for designing, implementing, and assessing citizen engagement initiatives, particularly in crisis response scenarios. It offers practical recommendations and best practices that can be also applied to organizing and running hackathons (Oikonomou, Boichenko, & Zourou, 2023).

5. Art Events

Art possesses a unique ability to address and illuminate social problems, to foster dialogue, reflection, and action. In order to engage the community in discussion, an art event can serve as a powerful tool to reflect on today's global issues. Typically, an exhibition opening features the artist who created it, and they describe the purpose of the exhibition, how it was created, the hidden meanings behind it, and the main message they hope to convey to the audience. To engage the audience, the artist can make a presentation using slides, show videos, ask questions, and share their personal experiences. After the opening of the exhibition, the works may remain on display for several months, allowing them to be seen by an even larger audience.

Art events can attract a diverse audience consisting of individuals looking to expand their horizons, including but not limited to:

- academic community members: people who appreciate art and attend events to enjoy and learn about it and are interested in the main theme of the exhibition;
- citizens: local residents who attend to support the event and their community;
- cultural institutions: museums, cultural centers, and other institutions that might collaborate or participate.
- professional artists: who are interested in this field;

Table 5. Recommendations to prepare art events

Date and time	Avoid clashes with major holidays or other events. Consider timing that is the most suitable for your target group.
Location and venue	Book a venue where the exhibition will be displayed in advance, and ensure the venue has enough space for the exhibition to be displayed, participants, and coffee break.
Exhibition content	Ensure you will receive or prepare exhibits in advance and have enough time to display the exhibition. Exhibits should have clear and informative labels.
Marketing and promotion	Prepare a marketing plan and use social media platforms to reach a wider audience. Produce posters, flyers, invitations, and digital content.
Form a Team	Curator, event manager, marketing team, volunteers (assign responsibilities and establish a task timeline).

Post-Exhibition Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carefully dismantle and pack artworks. • Collect feedback from participants and attendees for future improvements. • Assess the exhibition's success against initial goals.
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6. Youth Debate Tournament

The University of Latvia organized a youth debate tournament focused on the ongoing war in Ukraine and exploring ways to support Ukrainian citizens, including students. This event aimed to engage Bachelor students in a thought-provoking educational experience. The event began with a visit to the War Museum, which provided historical context to deepen participants' understanding of warfare's impacts, fostering a reflective and informed discussion. The visit lasted approximately two hours, an optimal duration for this exhibition. However, checking with the organizers for the exact time required to go through the exhibition would be advisable. The group size was 25 participants, which is the maximum number to ensure everyone could comfortably view the exhibits and participate in guided discussions.

The following day, the debate tournament took place. The debate sessions were designed to last about one and a half hours, with breaks between rounds to keep participants energized and engaged. The debate was structured based on the World Schools Debate format, providing a robust framework for discussing the topics. In this case, there were 8 teams of 3 members each, with one participant remaining who was a timekeeper. The debate tournament started with a 10-minute introduction session.

Teams were then assigned, and the roles of each member were detailed to set clear expectations. The first round of debates spanned 30 minutes and featured two parallel debates. Each debate included four teams, with two teams on each side. Each debate session lasted approximately 15 minutes, and this format was repeated for the second set of four teams. A 10-minute break followed the first round. During this break, judges gave the teams quick and constructive feedback from the first round. The final round, also lasting 30 minutes, featured the top two teams competing in a head-to-head debate from the first round. The total time for the final debate was approximately 15 minutes. After the debate, judges took 5 minutes to deliberate and provide their feedback. The event concluded with brief remarks from the organizers.

This format ensured that all participants had ample opportunity to speak and listen, fostering a dynamic and inclusive environment. The primary goal was to enhance students' global awareness, critical thinking, and public speaking skills. Participants gained a deeper understanding of the conflict, developed their debating abilities, and were inspired to engage in social action. To conclude the event, a summary session was

held where key points from the debates were reviewed, and participants reflected on their experiences.

Potential risks to consider:

Risk 1: Emotional sensitivity. To address emotional sensitivity, it was imperative to ensure the discussion leader was well-versed in the topic and known to the students, thus promoting a safe and supportive environment

Risk 2: Language barriers. Language barriers were addressed by ensuring translations were available at the event, creating a safe and welcoming environment where everyone felt encouraged to express themselves. The event environment was made welcoming and comfortable for all attendees, promoting open communication. Apps were utilized to provide instant translations, helping to bridge communication gaps during informal interactions.

Risk 3: Engagement levels. To maintain high levels of engagement, various interactive elements were incorporated throughout the event. This included providing quizzes related to the exhibits and encouraging discussions with video materials regarding the creation of the exhibit materials, if available.

Supplementing Materials:

1. [Debate Tournament Guidelines](#)

This document provides an overview of the debate organization process, including agenda and activities.

Participants' feedback

One important feature of successful citizen engagement event implementation is the constant gathering of participants' feedback. Baltics4UA consortium partners strive to gather feedback from almost every organized event, which helps to improve future formats. Therefore, it is advisable to include feedback gathering as an integral part of organizing an event. Usually, we send the feedback form after the event has taken place; however, the procedure heavily depends on your institutional rules. For instance, at UT, participants are asked to consent to receive the feedback form via email upon registration. This is a respectful way to approach participants for feedback and ensures their agreement to receive it.

In the feedback form, we typically ask about participants' backgrounds, including their country of residence and professional background. We also include general questions about their overall satisfaction, allowing them to give a certain grade, whether they are likely to participate in similar events, and if it increased their motivation to engage in citizen actions to support Ukraine. These questions help us measure the impact of our events and link to the project's topic.

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